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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****ACADEMIC CHEATING AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS**

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Article Received: March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

Academic dishonesty, academic misconduct, academic fraud and academic integrity are related concepts that refer to various actions on the part of students that go against the expected norms of a school, university or other learning institution. A total of 110 students was included in the study. The mean age of the students was 22.23 ± 1.23 years. There were 54 (49%) females and 56 (51%) males in the study. According to 20% of the students, they never cheated during the examination or internal assessments, 35% responded that they cheated occasionally i.e. once or twice during their examination. Forty five percent of the students said they always cheat during the examination. According to this study, there are a lot of students who cheat during the examination i.e. occasional or always. The various reasons of cheating must be evaluated, and proper policy should be made to minimize this issue.

Keywords: *Academic cheating, dishonesty, medical students*

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INTRODUCTION:

Academic dishonesty, academic misconduct, academic fraud and academic integrity are related concepts that refer to various actions on the part of students that go against the expected norms of a school, university or other learning institution. Definitions of academic misconduct are usually outlined in institutional policies.[1][2][3] academic dishonesty has been documented in every type of educational setting from elementary school to graduate school. Throughout history this type of dishonesty has been met with varying degrees of penalties.

There is a lack of research on academic misconduct (especially related to cheating behavior) in medical schools, and only scant reports are available from the universities of middle eastern countries. Additionally, there are currently no local or regional studies available that discuss the sensitive issue of cheating among medical students. Thus, no strict rules or punishment options have been suggested or implemented as a preventive measure for cheating. The socio-cultural background, religious belief, ethical values and attitude of the people living in the Pakistan are different than that of people living elsewhere. Therefore, there is no guarantee that similar rules or punishments will work in this region. Considering the facts mentioned above about the various types of academic misconduct, the present study was conducted at a different medical colleges of Pakistan to determine the prevalence and predisposing factors responsible for cheating among students and suggests ways to prevent this academic misconduct.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted in different medical colleges of Pakistan. The data was collected from students of different classes on a predefined proforma. Different Likert type questions were asked. All the responses were collected and analyzed in SPSS Ver. 25.0. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. Relevant statistical analysis was performed.

RESULTS:

A total of 110 students was included in the study. The mean age of the students was 22.23 ± 1.23 years, mean age of the females was 21.43 ± 0.23 years and mean age of males was 23.67 ± 1.11 years. There were 54 (49%) females and 56 (51%) males in the study. According to 20% of the students, they never cheated during the examination or internal assessments, 35% responded that they cheated occasionally i.e. once or twice during their examination. Forty five percent of the students said they always cheat during the examination. Regarding the ways of cheating responses were different i.e. using books, mobiles and asking from the friend etc. When asked about the reasons of cheating, 70% said they cheat because of fear of failure or lower marks. Other responses were to get good marks, habitual, way of methodology of teachers are not up to the mark and exams are difficult etc.

DISCUSSION:

Cheating can have negative impacts on honesty in the workplace and the quality of the healthcare system [4,5]. This study investigated the sensitive topic of cheating. Cheating can take the form of crib notes, looking over someone's shoulder during an exam, or any forbidden sharing of information between students regarding an exam or exercise. Many elaborate methods of cheating have been developed over the years. For instance, students have been documented hiding notes in the bathroom toilet tank, in the brims of their baseball caps, up their sleeves, along their thighs or in their cleavage. Also, the storing of information in graphing calculators, pagers, cell phones, and other electronic devices has cropped up since the information revolution began. While students have long surreptitiously scanned the tests of those seated near them, some students actively try to aid those who are trying to cheat. Methods of secretly signalling the right answer to friends are quite varied, ranging from coded sneezes or pencil tapping to high-pitched noises beyond the hearing range of most teachers. Some students have been known to use more elaborate means, such as using a system of repetitive body signals like hand movements or foot jerking to distribute answers (i.e. where a tap of the foot could correspond to answer "A", two taps for answer "B", and so on). Cheating differs from most other forms of academic dishonesty, in that people can engage in it without benefiting themselves academically at all. For example, a student who illicitly telegraphed answers to a friend during a test would be cheating, even though the student's own work is in no way affected. Another example of academic dishonesty is a dialogue between students in the same class but in two different time periods, both of which a test is

scheduled for that day. If the student in the earlier time period informs the other student in the later period about the test, that is considered academic dishonesty, even though the first student has not benefited him or herself. One other method is taking advantage of time zones, particularly in exams administered worldwide. Those who take the exam first (likely in Oceania) can then post answers for those about to take the exam (in a time zone behind like Europe).

CONCLUSION:

According to this study, there are a lot of students who cheat during the examination i.e. occasional or always. The various reasons of cheating must be evaluated, and proper policy should be made to minimize this issue.

Conflict of interest:

There was not conflict of interest.

REFERENCES:

1. Bretag, T., Mahmud, S., Wallace, M., Walker, R., James, C., Green, M., . . . Partridge, L. (2011). Core elements of exemplary academic integrity policy in Australian higher education. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 7(2), 3-12.
2. Bretag, T., Mahmud, S., East, J., Green, M., & James, C. (2011). Academic integrity standards: A preliminary analysis of the Academic integrity policies at Australian Universities. Paper presented at the Proceedings of AuQF 2011 Demonstrating Quality, Melbourne.
3. Eaton, Sarah Elaine (2017-01-17). "Comparative Analysis of Institutional Policy Definitions of Plagiarism: A Pan-Canadian University Study". *Interchange*. 48 (3): 271–

281. doi:10.1007/s10780-017-9300-7.
hdl:1880/106472. ISSN 0826-4805.
4. "Western Libraries Off-Campus Access To Electronic Resources".
login.proxy1.lib.uwo.ca. Retrieved 2020-03-11.
5. "Clampdown on timezone cheats". BBC News.
BBC. 2002-01-29. Retrieved 9 March 2017.